

THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN EDUCATION AND ITS IMPACT ON TEACHER-STUDENT RELATIONSHIP

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays mass media plays an important role in every sphere of our life. With that being said, education is also advancing day by day. It isn't confined to the four walls of a classroom anymore. Mass Media is responsible for this development to an extent. In this article, we will learn about the Role of Mass Media in Education and teacher-student relationship.

Both the "information explosion" and the "population explosion" are major issues in the modern world. A knowledge explosion is the result of the information explosion. Today, thanks to the developing universe of information, social and technological developments are happening quickly all across the world. Thus, knowledge is expanding rapidly. The horizon of human knowledge and comprehension is rapidly growing as new scientific frontiers open up every day.

On the other hand, there is a population expansion that goes hand in hand with the explosion of knowledge. With various levels of desire and aspiration, the student population is growing significantly year after year as a result of population increase and the democratization of education. The "population explosion" issue is more problematic in developing nations than it is in wealthy nations.

Because there are now more things to learn and more people to teach, the two general elements of "information explosion" and "population explosion" have created serious issues for education. The use of diverse mass communication channels in educational technology is crucial for resolving these issues successfully. With the aid of this mass media under educational technology, both qualitative improvement and quantitative growth of education can be facilitated and expedited. Therefore, the media has stepped in to help us solve this issue.

By fostering creativity, activity, and efficiency in its students, education of the future will be better able to fulfill its purpose. Education cannot be successful by solely using mechanical approaches in place of human ones. In order to teach more people better and faster, it is not enough to simply replace human teachers with mechanical ones. New patterns that combine both human and technical developments must be developed[2; 4-5-p].

There are several different mass communication media, including radio, television, newspapers, and movies, among others. Illustrative mass media were formerly used sparingly and on an individual basis. In the educational process, there was neither unified thought nor a scientific organization of these resources. However, the curiosity and initiative of some teachers have been largely responsible for their expanded use.

A piece of knowledge or information is transmitted to us through a communication medium. The message, which is more significant, is conveyed through this medium. Because the same information will appear different and have a completely different impact on us when it is presented to us orally, on a printed page, on the phone, on the radio, or on television. Therefore, the channel via which information is conveyed determines how effective it is. Thus, the mass-media are not only the messages, but also the message[11; 174-175-p].

Because it motivates the sensory organs to respond actively by massaging them. As a result, the mass media plays a crucial role in the teaching process in classrooms. The major goal is to use a variety of media to enhance the teaching and learning process. Therefore, obtaining better education or helping more students while using fewer teachers is the primary goal of mass media in education.

In fact, the mass media have permeated every aspect of modern life and have become a major source of information. They may be utilized and are currently being used as a tool for education. Therefore, the relevance of mass media in education is growing every day.

Importance of Mass Media:

1. The mass media are important because they quickly inform the population.
2. It requires comprehensive coverage of news covering everything happening everywhere in the world.
3. It opens up the entire universe to the person or class. Children can imagine, hear, and learn about the world while spending hours together in front of the television.
4. These media are easily accessible to audiences, allow for recurrent use, provide greater reality, shape attitudes, illustrate cause-and-effect links, and ultimately inspire viewers.
5. It facilitates distance learning by delivering information to far-off places.
6. It promotes attitude change, instills desirable values, and increases knowledge of cultural heritage.
7. The media plays a role in social change.
8. Interpersonal communication and group dynamics can be strengthened through the usage of mass media.
9. Mass media as means of communication make ideas clear to children and help them to acquire correct knowledge. They help in simplifying and in giving vividness to explanation.
10. Mass Media make the instruction concrete and stimulate interest and excite curiosity in things.

Education today, therefore, has a far greater responsibility than it had ever before. It has to meet the demands of a dynamic world which change its character every day. Contemporary education has to be more comprehensive and complete than before. As a result, both the role of the mass media, such as television, radio, cinema, and newspapers, as well as the many agencies of education, such as the home, society, community, etc., has expanded. Therefore,

media like the press, radio, movies, television, etc., are becoming more and more significant in people's lives nowadays [10; 361-363-p].

Press, radio, movies, TV, and other forms of mass media are used in teaching. There are a lot of mass media outlets, which are properly referred to as passive educational agencies. They indirectly affect people's attitudes and behaviors. These organizations work to improve people's moral judgment and moral tone while providing entertainment, educational propaganda, and historical records.

Following is a discussion of some significant mass media's roles:

(A) Radio: Radio serves as a mass communication medium. It is primarily utilized to broadcast events to distant parts of the globe. It is a significant source of entertainment as well. We listen to many radio talks, debates, and conversations every day. These are very significant and beneficial for the students. Many programs are aired over the radio, particularly for educational purposes. Radio is a powerful tool for both entertainment and education. It broadcasts cultural and scientific facts. It educates the general people. It sparks people's interests and curiosity.

The radio has shown to be a useful addition to classroom instruction and learning. Broadcasting for educational purposes is a relatively young venture that is doing successfully. Expert teaching in science, social studies, art, music, languages, politics, current events, and other areas can be provided through educational broadcasts, providing information and enrichment for both students and teachers[4; 2-3-p].

The educational programs are broadcasted by the teachers in order to provide them with effective methods that demonstrate new ideas and approaches to classroom procedures. In foreign schools, programs are specially designed in collaboration with experts for various age groups.

The following are the benefits of using radio as a form of mass media in education:

1. Educational radio programs encourage "listening participation." In recent history: The emphasis in radio is on sound rather than picture. Many educational programs are broadcast on the radio, and exceptional events are brought directly into the classroom from the source. An educational program may be preceded by an introduction by the class teacher and followed by a lengthy debate among students on the subject-matter under the broadcast discussion as part of classroom teaching. A gifted instructor may choose to educate via radio for the benefit of his or her students. As a result, key events, elections, inventions, political developments in other countries, and other current issues can be heard and debated in the classroom.

2. Educational radio broadcasts are an efficient way to introduce music, drama, and appreciation:

Radio is an important source of entertainment as well. Various radio talks, debates, and discussions are extremely informative and useful. Different subjects can be presented to students in the form of dramatized programs. Educational radio excels at dramatization, dialogue, musical features, and other creative programs that are not possible in the classroom.

3. Educational radio broadcasts are examples of team teaching:

The radio also allows students to participate in various programs such as quiz competitions, travel talks, plays, stories, lesson development, projects, and work programs in

the form of team teaching demonstrations. It should be organized through the collaborative efforts of the best resources in consultation with specialists and other subject experts. While completing the program, subject content, curriculum validity, age group suitability, and teaching methods should be considered.

4. Local teachers and students participate in educational radio broadcasts:

Well-planned radio broadcasts are presented in such a way that local teachers and students actively participate. As a result, prior to the broadcast, there should be preliminary research and discussion on the subject. The class may be encouraged to participate in follow-up discussions, projects, or creative activities through broadcast suggestions. Before presenting the program, both teachers and students should thoroughly prepare the material. They should use all available resources to create a high-quality program that is worth listening to in terms of content, speech, style, audibility, and presentability.

5. Radio for educational purposes:

Broadcasting helps to make learning an open system in the long run: educational radio can offer corrective programs for self-learning by individuals. It can reach participants while they are at work, at play, in the drawing room, or at recreational centers, transcending all boundaries and constraints imposed by formal education. Because learning directly from the teacher is limited, and there is a growing emphasis on a system of open learning to overcome the rigidities of formal education, there is a greater emphasis on learning through various mass media. Educational radio broadcasts are expected to play an important role in an open learning system. The non-formal approaches of educational radio can supplement the de-schooling society movement. All of the programs aim to create a learning society in which everyone can learn at any time and from any location.

Radio is now not only a popular form of mass media, but also a potential instructional tool in formal, informal, and non-formal education. It is now emphasizing the planning and production of science programs in both the formal and informal spheres of educational broadcasting. As a result, radio is an effective medium. It has played an important role in communication. It also has a significant impact on education. It not only educates but also inspires. It instills not only values and virtues, but also attitudes, interests, and appreciation.

Television (b):

Television is now an extremely popular source of entertainment for everybody. We watch the television and listen to the speaker's instructions. As a result, the task engages the learner's entire personality. As a result, it has become the most important and powerful mass communication agency.

In television, news items are not only read aloud, but also shown. As a result, not only are problems discussed, but practical remedies and solutions are also proposed. As a result, educational television is the most recent audio-visual medium used in classroom instruction. Television, through short films on historical sites, museums, and so on, can provide a very good understanding of the country's history. As a result, television plays an important role in mass media education.

Benefits of Educational Television:

There are numerous benefits to watching educational television. Young people watching television can get a very good idea of what happened.

Students can see how science has advanced for themselves:

- (1) Educational television has the potential to provide many previously unavailable learning experiences.
- (2) Educational television promotes ongoing collaboration among teachers, supervisors, learning materials experts, and skilled production teams.
- (3) Good and effective educational television broadcasts are the result of curriculum planning, content analysis, and the selection of the best instructional media.
- (4) It can use a variety of audio-visual aids, such as motion pictures, film strips, slides, recordings, drawings, maps, and other projected and non-projected aids. Television videotapes and recordings show the launch of space rockets, as well as political and social events.
- (5) Educational television gives birth to a new type of teaching team.
- (6) It can teach young people about past culture, history, and social life.
- (7) It can motivate both children and adults because it is both educational and entertaining.
- (8) Televised lectures are more exciting because they provide listeners with not only verbal information and instruction from the speaker, but also his entire personality engaged in the task.
- (9) National issues such as population, poverty, and illiteracy are frequently highlighted and discussed on television.
- (10) It plays an important role in educating children about our country's history and culture. It provides a good overview of the country's history by airing various programs such as dances, short films on historical sites, museums, and so on.

As a form of mass media, television plays an important role in educating the masses. It is a dynamic and powerful medium that has an impact on education. Its effective application is based on the fundamental psychological principles of learning that apply to all successful learning processes.

(c) The Press:

The Press covers the entire printed matter. These printed matters are books, magazines, journals or newspapers. Reading material has enormous potential. It has a positive influence on people. It shapes people's attitudes and philosophies of life by acting on their intelligence and emotions.

An educated person is one who has an open mind, general awareness, and knowledge of his surroundings. His knowledge base is vast and diverse. Newspapers make a significant contribution to education for the purposes stated above. The press not only reports on events, but it also expresses its own opinions on them. As a result, the reader is given the opportunity to consider an issue from a variety of perspectives. The press also aids in the study of history, geography, science, literature, and other subjects. Newspapers add to our understanding of these subjects[3; 6-7-p].

Certain topics can be linked to everyday life through the press, newspapers and other journals or their e-versions. The students must be aware of what is going on in his surroundings. As a result, the press provides an important service to education by educating children about current events. The press may bring earthquakes, cyclones, new planets, and political changes to the attention of students. It also contains a wealth of historical

information. This press has the potential to expand and improve the student's limited knowledge of history. As a result, the press will be an important medium of education and instruction.

Principles of Using Mass Media: The teacher should make all necessary arrangements for effectively using mass media. He should choose the appropriate media according to the students' ages. He must understand some general principles of mass media usage.

1. Organization: Mass media should be organized as a component of educational programs. They should not be separated from the rest of the curriculum.
2. Selection: The teacher should properly select and coordinate mass media. An experienced and trained teacher can choose the appropriate media for the students' needs.
3. Planning: Depending on the needs of the instructional program, mass media should be made available. Teachers should be proficient in the use of mass media. They should receive specialized training in preparation. As a result, they must be carefully planned.
4. Experience: The media should be related to the students' experiences.
5. Preparation: Students should be adequately prepared. Before using it, the teacher should prepare himself. He should understand what the media teaches and how it fits into his lesson plan. Adequate preparation should be followed by an appropriate presentation and follow-up.
6. Evaluation: Mass media should be evaluated on a regular basis in terms of their use, impact on learning.

Conclusion: The media has proven to be useful in categorizing concepts, stimulating group and individual activities, developing a collective critical awareness, changing attitudes, imposing a new structure or organization on specific subjects, and encouraging originality and creativity. As a result, teachers must be properly motivated and interested in using such materials. They must also be trained and orientated in the proper use and maintenance of the materials.

As we all know, good teachers are created rather than born. Training in methods, techniques, and the use of various means and media aids a teacher's ability to be effective and efficient. All illustrative materials will serve as "aids" to his instruction. His educational outputs will be optimized through the judicious application of modern methods, techniques, means, and media. Educational research has also shown that by carefully selecting and utilizing modern communication media, instruction can be greatly improved.

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